

KINETIC DETERMINATION OF THIOSULPHATE IN TRACE AMOUNTS

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Abstract

Thiosulphate is a sulphur containing ligand which has quite evident in its chemical formula as $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$. The sulphur atom present in thiosulphate inhibits the Mercury catalyzed substitution reaction between hexacyanoferrate (II) and Phenanthroline [Phen]. The inhibition of the reaction takes place since the catalyst has a strong affinity to bind with the inhibitor. This inhibitor-catalyst reaction thus competes with the ligand substitution reaction between the hexacyanoferrate (II) and the phenanthroline. The reaction was studied spectrophotometrically at 528nm in aqueous medium and a dark green coloured complex compound, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{Phen}]^{3-}$ was formed. The chosen reaction conditions were: $\text{pH} = 3.0 \pm 0.02$, $\text{temp.} = 25.0 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$, ionic strength (μ) = 0.05M (KNO_3). Linear calibration graphs were recorded at different times (A_t) and several concentrations of thiosulphate, under the chosen reaction conditions. The detection limit for thiosulphate was recorded at $6 \times 10^{-7}\text{M}$, equilibrium constant for the complex of inhibitor and catalyst i.e. K_{Cl} , the Michaelis-Menten constant i.e. K_m and equilibrium constant for the complex of substrate and catalyst i.e. K_s were calculated from the data so obtained kinetically. A general mechanism of the reaction has also been proposed.

Keywords: Thiosulphate, Inhibition Effect, Kinetic, Phenanthroline, Hexacyanoferrate (II)

Introduction

Thiosulphate is a colourless compound and is used as a chlorine neutralizer in swimming pools. Its Medical uses comprise as an antidote to cyanide poisoning. Thiosulfate serves as a sulfur donor for the conversion of cyanide to thiocyanate and therefore it can then be safely excreted by urination, this reaction is catalysed by the enzyme rhodanase. For this purpose it is used together with sodium nitrite. Apart from such utilities it can also become toxic and its toxic range for humans when injected intravenously is 0.2 to 1.5 g/kg . Secondly Ingestion of 12 g of sodium thiosulfate was virtually non-toxic except

for producing violent catharsis. Therefore, it needs to be monitored in such cases.

Numerous kinetic studies of metal catalysed N- Heterocyclic ligand substitution reaction of hexacyanoferrate (II) have been studied¹⁻³. Trace determination of many inorganic ions have also been investigated⁴⁻¹⁵. Addition of a complexing agent to a metal catalysed reaction may result in either promotion or inhibition of the reaction. Linear relation of the added ligand can often be obtained by simple empirical treatment of rate data. This forms the basis of determination of small amounts of complexing agents by the Method Known as "Kinetic Method" developed by us here.

We have already studied the Kinetic determination of Hg (II) at trace levels using its catalytic effect on ligand substitution reaction between hexacyanoferrate (II) and Phenanthroline[2]. The reaction was followed spectrophotometrically at 528n.m. (λ_{max} of a dark coloured complex $[Fe(CN)_5Phen]^{3-}$). The above cited indicator reaction is used for determination of sulphur containing ligands like cysteine⁷. These ligands have high formation metal constants than those of the ligands containing N and O atoms even at low pH values and are thus best suited for the study. Like Cysteine, thiosulphate also forms chelates with Hg (II) and inhibit the rate of the indicator reaction. The optimum conditions for the indicator reaction like concentration of reagents, temperature, pH and ionic strength have been studied here.

There is limited information available in literature to determine these complexing agents^{23,24} by metal catalysed reactions¹⁵⁻²². Moreover, the analysis requires expensive instruments of voltametry and others^{25,26}. Therefore, the need for a simple and less expensive technique is always required. The present paper describes the determination of thiosulphate in trace levels based on its inhibitory effect of the Mercury catalysed ligand substitution reaction between hexacyanoferrate (II) and Phenanthroline.

Experimental

Materials

Double distilled water was used throughout to prepare all solutions. All the chemicals used in this study were of analytical reagent grade. The solution of $K_4[Fe(CN)_6] \cdot 3H_2O$ (AR,E. Merck, Germany) was prepared by weighing a desired amount and kept in dark in coloured bottles. The fresh solutions of Phenanthroline (S.D. Fine Chemicals) was prepared in double distilled water everyday before starting the kinetic run. A stock solution of $HgCl_2$ (BDH) was prepared by weighing and dissolving $HgCl_2$ in water. Dilute solutions of $HgCl_2$ were also prepared daily in order to prevent loss due to its adsorption on glass surfaces. KNO_3 (A.R. Glaxo) was used to maintain ionic strength in reaction medium. Thiosulphate was standardized iodometrically against standard

$K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution²⁷. The pH of the reaction mixture was maintained at a desired value using potassium phthalate(A.R. Qualigens Fine chemicals) -sodium Hydroxide buffer²⁸.

Apparatus

All the reactant solutions were equilibrated at 25°C by keeping them inside environmental chamber in order to maintain the desired temperature within the accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ C$, Genesis model No. 10UV was used to record the spectra of the reaction. The pH measurements were made on a digital pH meter of Sio-global pH meter.

Procedure

1 ml of Hg^{+2} solution of a fixed concentration was taken and 1ml of inhibitor or complexing agent of various concentrations were mixed and kept for 10 minutes to ensure formation of CI. Then 3ml of buffer followed by 1ml of phenanthroline of specific concentration was added. The reaction was started by adding 1ml of Ferrocyanide solution. The reaction mixture was shaken vigorously and then transferred to a cuvette of 1cm path length kept in a cell compartment maintained at $25.0\pm 0.1^\circ C$. A fixed time procedure at 528 n.m. was used for measuring the initial rate to establish the calibration curves.

The chosen reaction conditions are $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-} = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Phen] = 2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, $[Hg^{+2}] = 7.0 \times 10^{-3}$ pH= 3.0 ± 0.02 , temp.= $25.0 \pm 0.1^\circ C$, ionic strength (μ) = $0.05 M$ (KNO_3).

Results And Discussion

The Phenanthroline substitution of the co-ordinated cyanide in hexacyanoferrate (II) is homegenoslycatalysed by (Hg^{+2}) ions in acidic medium at normal temperature. A detailed kinetic and mechanistic study of this reaction has already been studied. Traces of (Hg^{+2}) ions enhance the rate of the reaction to a very good extent and the reaction rate was followed spectrophotometrically at 528nm, due to the formation of product $[Fe(CN)_5Phen]^{3-}$. The studies show that there is no interference from the reactants $[Hg^{+2}]$, $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$, $[Phen]$. The concentration of thiosulphate was varied from mole ratio 0.1 to 5. The absorbance changes observed for cysteine system after a fixed time interval are given in Table1.

Table 1. Determination of cysteine by its inhibitory effect on Hg^{2+} catalysed substitution of cyanide in $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$ by phen,

Thiosulphate taken $\times 10^6 M$	A_t Absorbance after t minutes	
	A_{15}	A_{20}
18.32	0.169	0.176
14.51	0.182	0.195

10.46	0.199	0.201
8.32	0.210	0.215
6.02	0.238	0.252
4.21	0.272	0.331

Under conditions: $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-} = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[Phen] = 2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[Hg^{2+}] = 7.0 \times 10^{-7} M$, $pH = 3.0 \pm 0.02$, $temp. = 25 \pm 0.1^\circ C$, $I = 0.05 M$

Effect of pH on the Reaction rate.

The pH dependence of the reaction rate was studied in the pH range 1-8 at 3 time points at A_t (where $t = 10, 15, 20$ min). The change in absorbance at 528 nm as a function of pH is shown in Fig 1. Here, the rate of the reaction is slow at lower pH, attains a maximum value at $pH = 3.0 \pm 0.02$, then falls off again. This decrease is attributed to the deficiency of protons needed to regenerate the catalytic species or due to decrease in $[Hg^{+2}]$ as a result of hydrolytic precipitation. Thus, pH value of 3.0 ± 0.02 becomes critical for this system and should be maintained at optimum value to losing sensitivity required for the determination using phthalate – sodium hydroxide buffer²⁸.

Fig 1. Effect of pH on the Hg(II)- catalysed substitution of CN^- in hexacyanoferrate(II) by $[Phen]$: Conditions: $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-} = 1.50 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[Phen] = 1.50 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Hg^{2+}] = 1.5 \times 10^{-5} M$, $\mu = 0.03 M (KNO_3)$ and temperature = $25.0 \pm 0.1^\circ C$

Effects of Reagent Concentration, Temperature and Ionic strength

The effect of phenanthroline concentration was studied at the optimum pH and a [Phen] range $2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}$, to $3.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$. On the basis of studies done, it was revealed the rate of reaction increases linearly up to the concentration $2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$ and then finally levels off at $[\text{Phen}] \geq 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$. Thus, the [Phen] of $2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$ was selected as optimal.

The effect of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ on the initial rate was studied in the range 1.5×10^{-4} to $2.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{M}$, keeping all other values constant. The plot of log initial rate vs log $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ shows a variable order dependence on $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ changing from first order at lower concentrations to a fractional order at higher concentrations but certainly not tending towards zero. A $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ of $2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$ was chosen optimal.

The influence of temperature on the rate of the catalysed and uncatalysed reaction was studied in the range of $20-50^\circ\text{C}$. The reaction obeyed Eyring equation and maximum rate was achieved at 25°C which was selected for further studies. The effect of ionic strength (μ) on the rate of catalysed reaction in the range 0.02 to 0.05M, showed increase and then decrease in the reaction rate. An ionic strength of 0.05M gives measurable change in absorbance values, which was selected for further studies.

For analytical applications, the catalytic effect of $[\text{Hg}^{2+}]$ on the rate of catalysed reaction was studied in the range $2.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{M}$ to $9.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{M}$ under the conditions, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-} = 2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}$, $[\text{phen}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$, $\text{pH} = 3.0 \pm 0.02$, temperature = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$, $\mu = 0.05 \text{M}$ (KNO_3). The plot of absorbance after 10min (A_{10}) vs. $[\text{Hg}^{2+}]$ was found to be linear in the $[\text{Hg}^{2+}]$ range of $4.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{M}$ to $9.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{M}$. A $[\text{Hg}^{2+}]$ of $7.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{M}$ provides sufficient absorbance change, and hence was used for determination of. Thiosulphate.

Kinetic Role of inhibiting ligands

Based on the consideration that Inhibitor cysteine is competitive with the catalyst²⁹ and is reversible, for the Mercury catalysed reaction between phenanthroline and hexacyanoferrate (II), thereby depleting the concentration of catalyst and reducing the rate of the reaction. The reaction scheme proposed earlier³⁰ and modified to include the rate of inhibitor denoted by I, is outlined below:

If we take $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ present in non-rate limiting excess condition as S and its initial concentration by $[\text{S}_0]$, it is simple to derive the rate expression by comparing it with enzyme catalysed reaction of a single substrate in presence of an inhibitor. The reaction rate in presence of catalyst can be given by equation (1)

$$\frac{1}{V_0} = \frac{1}{V_{\max}} + \frac{K_m}{V_{\max}} \cdot \frac{1}{[S_0]}$$

This equation can be transformed to Line Weaver-Burk ³¹form as Equation (2) as under

$$V_0 = \frac{V_{\max}}{1 + \frac{K_m}{[S_0]}}$$

Here, V_0 is the reaction rate in presence of catalyst only V_{\max} is the maximum attainable rate at a particular catalyst concentration in presence of a non-rate limiting quantity of substrate and K_m is the Michaelis-Menten constant, which is roughly equivalent to the dissociation constant of the catalyst substrate complex. In presence of inhibitor, the rate of the reaction can be represented as equation (3)

$$V_i = \frac{V_{\max}}{1 + \frac{K'_m}{[S_0]}}$$

Where K'_m is the new apparent Michaelis-Menten constant in presence of the inhibitor. It can be shown that

$$K'_m = K_m \left[1 + \frac{[I_0]}{K'_{CI}} \right]$$

Substituting this value in Equation (3) we get

$$V_i = \frac{V_{\max}}{\frac{K_m}{[S_0]} \left[1 + \frac{[I_0]}{K'_{CI}} \right]}$$

Here, V_i is the reaction rate in presence of inhibitor (at a fixed catalyst concentration), and K'_{CI} is the dissociation constant of the catalyst inhibitor (C-I) complex.

Equation (5) can also be transformed to equation (6) in Line Weaver – Burk form as

$$\frac{1}{V_i} - \frac{1}{V_{\max}} = \frac{K_m}{V_{\max}[S_0]} + \frac{K_m}{V_{\max}[S_0]} \cdot \frac{[I_0]}{K'_{CI}} \quad (6)$$

In the above equation, V_{\max} is not an experimental quantity, but it is obtained from the intercept of the plot of $1/V_0$ vs $1/[S_0]$ from equation (2) in absence of inhibitor as shown in Figure 2. The slope of this plot gives the Value of K_m as 72.71 .

Fig. 2. Linear plot of $1/V_0$ Vs $1/[S_0]$: Conditions: $[Hg^{2+}] = 1.5 \times 10^{-6} M$, $[Phen] = 2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$, $pH = 3.0 \pm 0.02$, temperature = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ C$, $\mu = 0.03 M (KNO_3)$.

Equation (6) also works when the inhibitor 'I' forms a C-I type chelate with the catalyst 'C' and for this reaction no substrate inhibitor is seen. Under

these conditions a plot of $\left[\frac{1}{V_i} - \frac{1}{V_{\max}} \right]$ vs $[I_0]$ gives a straight line as shown in Figure 3. The intercept of this plot give a K_m that agrees with the value

calculated here by plotting $\frac{1}{V_0}$ vs $\frac{1}{[S_0]}$ the slope of which gives a K'_{CI} that corresponds to the cysteine complex of Mercury, as listed in Table2.

Fig. 3 Determination of K'_{CI} and K_m in presence of inhibitor thiosulphate: Conditions: $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-} = 3.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[Phen] = 1.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Hg^{2+}] = 7.5 \times 10^{-7} M$, $pH = 3.0 \pm 0.02$, $\mu = 0.05 M(KNO_3)$ and temperature = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ C$.

The reciprocal of this K_m is approximately equal to the stability constant K_s ($\log K_s = 1.91 \pm 0.98$) of the catalyst substrate complex. The values of the stability constant (K_{CI}) of the CI complexes and its reciprocal K'_{CI} are also given in Table 2. The competitive, non-competitive and incompetitive behavior of inhibiting ligands can also be differentiated, although this is beyond the scope of this study.

Table2. Conditional Formation constants under optimal conditions.

A.	Mercury - inhibitor Complex Inhibitor – Thiosulphate	$\log K_{CI}$ 6.12 ± 0.02
B.	Michaelis - Menten Constant Inhibitor – Thiosulphate	$\log K_m$ 1.79 ± 0.02
C.	Catalyst - Substrate Complex	$\log K_s$ 1.91 ± 0.03

Analytical Applications

The validity of the proposed method was tested by the recovery experiments performed on synthetic mixtures (SMs) of water sulphide ions as shown in Table 3. The synthetic mixture analysis results in a reasonably good recovery. Under the specified conditions, the detection limit for thiosulphate was $4.8 \times 10^{-7} M$.

Table 3.Determination of micro amounts of thiosulphate in Synthetic Mixtures

Synthetic Mixtures (SM)	Composition of SM (μM)	Found (μM) proposed Method	Recovery %
SM1	Cys (0.4) + S^{2-} (0.4)	0.40	100.0
SM2	Cys (0.4) + S^{2-} (1.0)	0.42	102.2
SM3	Cys (0.5) + S^{2-} (1.0)	0.51	101.7
SM4	Cys (0.9) + S^{2-} (1.0)	0.92	102.2

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